

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF CREATIVE INTELLECTUALS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AZERBAIJAN CULTURE (1960 – 1980s)

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Abstract

The important factors that play the decisive role in the formation and evolution of every nation are among the important and extremely significant processes that emerge in the course of historical events that humanity has always faced and thought about, on the scene of difficult and intense struggles and thanks to them. Thus, the process of formation, growth, purification and development of the nation is directly connected in the formation, emergence, evolution process of its intellectuals and other actual issues. When the society develops its intellectuals, it develops itself, constantly gaining the incomparable achievements in the various fields of education and science, strengthening its scientific potential and striving for innovations, development, progressive methods, realism and modern scientific achievements based on accurate facts. Every intellectual is the bright child of his nation, its healthy and progressive thinking, scientific potential, creative person and the very valuable treasure of science. The creativity of each intellectual means his main field of activity, the extremely valuable scientific achievements he has gained as a result of his hard work, effort and many years of intense struggle, the urgent problems he has raised, the works he has found solutions to and investigated, the new paths he has opened, the new areas of scientific research he has identified, the intense researches and searches he has conducted, the scientific results he has reached, the important scientific issues he has raised, etc. The intellectuals, working in these fields, constantly develop, improve, modernize, enrich them with the progressive ideas, and seek and find the solutions to problems that meet the requirements of modern science, thereby forming themselves as true scientists and intellectuals in this way. In this regard, the activity of creative intellectuals is the shining example of their talent and ability, skills and smartness. The scope of activity of the creative intellectuals is quite wide and covers all spheres of culture. The cultural problems are always very actual and distinguished by their diversity, uniqueness, characteristic features, reference to real facts, and at the same time, being the product of the artist's artistic imagination. The creative intellectual, as an artist, enriches the field he works in by working on it and makes it colorful with his creativity, as well as with his beautiful works, heroes, plots, talent, skills and abilities, as a result, the culture is enriched, with the different and unique creative colors it becomes interesting, attractive, thought provoking, perfect in terms of ideas, fluent, national in form, and realistic in content. In this regard, the role played by the creative intellectuals in the development of Azerbaijan culture is particularly noteworthy.

Keywords: creative intellectuals, creativity, Azerbaijan, culture, development, problems, activity, researches

Introduction

The development of culture is one of the main issues facing every society. The culture can be considered as one of the areas that plays the important role in the formation, improvement, progressive development and functioning of society in civil and legal aspects. As the culture develops, so does society, the education and science take on their true and colorful hues, ensuring that people walk on the right way, in the direction of progressive and conscious formation. From this point of view, the culture should be studied, propagated, disseminated, researched, investigated, and should be one of the decisive directions of relations. The study of culture is the multifaceted process and involves all its areas in the scientific research in the equally effective and fair manner. The scientific study, analysis, investigation of culture means ensuring its development away from its artistic and entertainment character and towards more realism, the logical explanation, interpretation, study and successful resolution of events. The culture is such field that should enlighten, teach, educate, guide and form not only the scientists and intellectuals,

but also other segments of society. All areas of culture are of exceptional importance in the formation of a person as a personality. The person who is familiar with the various areas of culture gradually forms these positive and realistic qualities in himself and begins to function in the society as the perfect and mature personality. Such people bravely face all the difficulties, tortures and injustices of the modern world and always win, becoming the real and vivid example of the image of the cultured, mature, educated, conscious and progressive person in life. The propaganda of culture is one of the most important issues. The propaganda is the most powerful and effective way of the modern world and plays the decisive role in the process of education and proper formation of people. Thus, the person who is familiar with the latest achievements of science and technology tries to bring these innovations into his real life, beauty, creativity, experience and daily activity. These efforts ultimately lead to the diverse development and renewal of the various spheres of culture, the spread of progressive ideas and trends to culture, and the progress of education and science. That is why the propaganda

of culture is of great importance and it should make the positive contribution to the upbringing, life, worldview and formation of people, not on the wrong path, but on the right path. In this regard, the study of culture can help to make the propaganda more efficient and effective, enriching it with the scientific facts, correct analyses and works. The process of studying culture requires the scientists to develop positive qualities such as great responsibility, intellectual conscience, endless hard work, broad outlook, etc., and only then can the problems facing the culture be properly studied. The culture is also one of the decisive directions of relations. Thus, people express their identity as the representatives of different nations in their works, handicrafts, creative examples, etc. in diverse forms, and enrich them with their workviews, talents and skills, progressive ideas, innovations and individual characteristic features. The role and activity of the creative intellectuals are of exceptional importance in this work.

1.The formation of creative intellectuals

Each era has its own requirements, criteria, development directions and trends. It is extremely important to keep up with the current socio – political environment and situation of the era, to have the deep understanding of it, to have the ability to analyze it, to solve it correctly, to always fight against difficulties, not to submit to injustice, not to remain silent in the face of injustice, to always listen to the voice of conscience and to form another superior and positive qualities in oneself and bring them to the creativity in completely different aspects. Thus it is important and purposeful for the ideologically mature person to take an active position in society [21, p.3]. A person is formed, developed, educated and become a personality in society. An artist, working conscientiously and responsibly in the various fields of culture, overcomes all the difficulties and obstacles on the way to professional craftsmanship, matures, specializes and gradually becomes the professional specialist, entering the honorable stage as the skilled connoisseur of his art. The culture, in all its spheres and directions, refers entirely to the creative

process. The creativity is the direct field of the activity of creative intellectuals and is based on the development strategy such as gradual learning, preparation, specialization, gaining experience, working, putting theoretical knowledge into the practical work, growth, maturity and comprehensive formation. An artist must always improve and develop his art, regardless of the society in which he lives. The creative intellectuals can be considered the creators, carriers, developers, disseminators of culture and the main means of expanding relations [21, p.8].

Finding the creative individuals in society, revealing their skills and abilities, not destroying talented and special – talented individuals, but rather preserving them, further developing this talent and preparing them as artists with a broad worldview, excellent education, deep knowledge of rare examples of art of world culture, comprehensive preparation and with exquisite taste can be considered one of the most important problems facing society and the period. The culture requires creativity. The creativity requires art and craftsmanship. The art must be created and developed by an artist. It is essential to reveal an artist as a rare talent, educate, teach, train, develop, mature and shape. The appropriate conditions should be created for the training of creative individuals, and the state's policy and strategy should not be based on the destruction of such talented children of the people, but on their preservation, protection, development and assistance in taking their worthy place in the modern complex world. The intellectuals engaged in the artistic creativity should strive to fulfill these tasks. The research scientist, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, who has studied the formation, activity and role of creative intellectuals very well, shows that the historical process combines the wide range of cultural events, and the artistic creativity occupies the important place in it. The artistic creativity is a cultural phenomenon. The development of culture is the integral part of the general historical process [21, p.10] (Image 1).

Image 1. The research scientist, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva

Everyone has the right to participate in cultural life, to use the cultural institutions and cultural resources. However, the creative intellectuals participate in this cultural process not as the spectators or listeners, but as the creative one. The creative intellectuals write beautiful works, compose playful, cheerful and rich music, create unique paintings, erect charming statues, prepare the projects for beautiful architectural monuments, play interesting roles and stage beautiful performances, screen deep and thought provoking documentaries and feature films, write librettos and scripts for them, compose various colorful and solemn music for performances, animation and movies. The training and formation of professional creative personnel – creative intellectuals who skillfully operate in such a wide range of fields require the special care, attention, assistance from the state, and the special state policy for the protection and preservation of creative individuals. From this point of view, the training of creative intellectuals in the republic in the 60 – 80s of the XXth century, the finding of talented individuals, the granting of freedom of creativity and activity to them, the improvement of their qualifications from time to time, the emergence of the concept of professional intellectuals – creators, the provision of state care for them, and the protection of creative individuals with refined taste from unpleasant situations and cruelty encountered in the society should be considered among the most important and actual issues facing the state, the people, and society.

During this period, the great importance was attached to aesthetic education in our country. In this regard, the promotion of self – activity and professional creativity by all means, the identification of only talented individuals completely gratuitously, their involvement in the cultural life of the country, their education in the relevant arts in order to engage in professional creativity, their study, internship, preparation, specialization and the solution of such issues were of great importance [22, p.3].

The various competitions, meetings, discussions, disputes, reports read by the professional artists in the various creative fields to young and talented creative individuals, creative reports, audience conferences, organization of performances by amateur and artistic amateur associations, activity of their leaders and employees, meetings with the members of drama associations and amateur collectives operating under the various military units and organizations and other such actual events play an exceptional role in the discovery and development of creative individuals. The scope of influence of the audience conferences held by the Azerbaijan Theater Society is very wide. Such conferences were attended by heads of organizations, heads and employees of drama clubs, representatives of the Baku City Public Education Department and members of other organizations. Thus, in 1971 – 1972, the Young Spectator Theater held more than 50 large – scale events on a city and regional scale. Among them theoretical conferences, organization of exhibitions of children's drawings, creative meetings of young poets and playwrights, etc. were of great importance. The young activists of the theater, united in the art club, created the sections for actors, theater critics, naturalistic design, etc. The main task of these associations and sections

was to identify, educate, prepare and shape talented individuals in the existing environment [17]. Thus, more than 15 thousand people participated in more than 20 audience conferences held in Baku in 1962 alone. The discussions of various films were held here, and important aspects such as the creation of films, the preparation of films, the writing, discussion, and filming of scripts, the organization of the work of actors and directors, the formation of actor – audience relations, the selection of a professional acting team, ensuring that the director's imagination does not harm the main idea of the work, artistic and design issues, etc. were in the spotlight. During this period, the newspaper "Movie updates", which began to be published in the republic in the 60s of the XXth century, covered in detail the advertising of motion pictures, the filming, preparation and distribution of cinematographic works, the activity of the creative team, the working principles and other creative issues [22, p.22].

The activity of the Union of Artists aimed at the development of fine arts and aesthetic education in secondary schools played the decisive role in the education of children and youth, their formation and activity as future creative individuals. Thus, the demand for works of fine arts in libraries increased, art exhibitions and writing of essays of the various contents related to individual works of art took on intensive character, exhibitions organized from children's handicrafts, decorating the class-rooms and corridors of schools with the best art and painting samples selected from handicrafts of talented children and youth, etc., encouraging and creative methods began to gain wide popularity. The members of the Union of Artists of the Republic gave 85 lectures in 1960 and 102 reports in 1962 [7; 9].

The role of folk universities in the process of emergence and formation of the creative intellectuals was of particular importance. Since 1959, the folk universities have begun to be established in Azerbaijan. The new branches of folk culture universities, which play an important role in the moral education of people, began to emerge and spread. Among them the university of music, the university of cinema, the university of social sciences, the film university of parents, the university of health, etc. were especially distinguished. The special attention was paid to the work and development of cultural universities. Thus, in order to properly direct the activity of folk cultural universities, the Republican Public Council was created, as well as another public council consisting of the representatives of cultural organizations, societies that disseminate the political and scientific knowledge – trade unions and creative unions [22, p.26 – 27]. In 1959, the University of Culture was organized within the Azerbaijan Composers' Union [1]. In 1961 alone, 84 lectures were delivered and creative meetings were held through the cultural universities [2].

In 1960, it was decided to create a special group of lecturers to strengthen the activity of cultural universities on the union and republican scale [5]. Thus, the Republican Union of Artists has begun the practical activity to assist the work of cultural universities organized in cultural palaces and various institutions [22, p.28]. The Union of Artists organized 67 lectures on the wide popularization of art and various issues of fine arts. The

artists and art critics delivered the speeches on the various topics “Azerbaijan applied art in 40 years”, “Types and genres of applied art”, etc. at folk universities established in the various institutions and organizations operating in Baku and the regions of the republic [6].

The Union of Cinematographers organized the group of 15 lecturers in 1960 – 1961 to assist the cultural universities. They delivered the lectures on various topics reflecting important issues facing the art of cinema, such as “How to Create a Motion Picture”, “How to Shoot a Motion Picture”, “On the History of Azerbaijan Cinema”, etc. The members of the Union of Cinematographers delivered more than 400 lectures at cultural universities during this period [22, p.28]. The Union of Cinematographers organized the folk faculty, folk university of cinema art at the “Vatan” cinema, film club, etc. In 1976 – 1980, the film scholars, critics, directors and actors held 165 workshops across the republic [25, p.9]. The folk film university was established at the “Azerbaijanfilm” studio. The talented and skilled young people were attracted to this university, who were trained to enter relevant institutes and make amateur films [22, p.29]. As can be seen, the cultural universities played the exceptional role in the sphere of identifying talented and specially gifted individuals, preparing them for future professional education, and forming them as prepared creative individuals in various fields.

In 1959, the directors and soloists of the Azerbaijan State Academic Opera and Ballet Theater gave the various lectures at cultural universities on topics such as “How to listen and understand music”, “Opera Art”, etc. [11].

By presenting topics of various natures, the audience of listeners and spectators had the opportunity to learn the intricacies of professional art, to deeply understand it, and to get favourable conditions for the emergence of talented and capable individuals who wanted to work through art. At the same time, the creative intellectuals represented in various creative unions, working and engaged in professional art, were striving to raise the level of the lectures and reports they gave. Depending on the nature of each activity, the visual and colorful illustrative materials were enriched and were increasingly accompanied by the screening of documentary films with topical content, performances by artists of the Opera and Ballet Theater, exhibitions, stands, the compilation of photo albums, the organization of photo galleries, the presentation of photo stands and videos collecting handicrafts and art samples of amateur and young creative individuals, etc. In addition, the various excursions of educational and moral significance organized to the historical and architectural monuments of Baku could also be considered one of the important elements in this regard. Such cultural universities, which combine several fields of art, played the very important role in finding, revealing, training, preparing creative individuals, enriching their worldview, acquiring creative knowledge, skills and gradually forming [22, p.29].

In the 60s and 70s of the XXth century, the number of folk universities operating in the republic increased. In 1968 – 1969, there were 237 folk universities with 26.900 listeners, in 1971 – 1972, there were 273 folk

universities with 36.198 listeners, and in 1979 – 1980, there were 671 folk universities with 123.700 listeners [22, p.29 – 30].

It should be noted that the activity of each folk university were evaluated not only by the number of listeners and lectures given there, but also by the quality of the classes, the impact of the lectures and classes on the listeners, and the diversity of effective creative forms, methods and techniques used by the artists working there in their search for talent. In folk universities, the diverse creative forms and methods such as seminars, debates, questions and answers, discussions, film screenings and audience discussions, etc., were sometimes used rather poorly. The theaters, concert organizations, film studios and other organizations also provided some assistance for the normal functioning of folk universities. However, it should also be noted that the level of regular practical activity and assistance provided by certain organizations to the folk universities in terms of assigning lecturers and providing them with relevant textbooks, teaching aids, etc. was somewhat low [22, p.30].

The Azerbaijan Creative Unions have constantly fought for the formation of the people in the ideological and educational environment in the country, purely creative atmosphere of talented individuals, and in general, people’s refined aesthetic taste and the professional art of creative intellectuals [22, p.35].

The self – activity creativity operating in the republic also played the unique role in the formation of creative intellectuals. In 1975, the cultural and artistic figures took care of some self – activity collectives in connection with the holding of the First Republican Festival of Artistic Self – Activity Creativity [22, p.39]. In this work, the Creative Unions also maintained the extensive contact with libraries, clubs and other cultural – educational institutions [22, p.46].

The “Creative Meetings Club”, established in the country in the 60s of the XXth century, included writers, composers, artists, architects, and other creative intellectuals. The purpose of organizing this club was to strengthen creative relations between the professional and young creative intellectuals working in various fields of literature and art in the country and to ensure the growth and formation of talented individuals in a purely creative environment [24].

The Republican Union of Composers actively participated in the creation of music clubs in the cities and regions of the country. The strengthening of the activity of music schools in the 70s of the XXth century allowed the creation of young musicians’ club and folk orchestras’ collectives [19].

The care for the development of artistic self – activity and supporting their activity were considered one of the main tasks of the creative unions. The folk theaters are the most widespread type of self – activity collectives. They are one of the active types of art that connect folk creativity with professional craftsmanship and play the important role in the formation of creative intelligentsia. As society developed, the process of mutual enrichment of artistic self – activity and professional art intensified. In the performances and speeches of folk creativity – artistic self – activity collectives, represented by various amateur associations and

groups, sometimes such elements, plots, structures and creative lines are found that are impossible to find in the performances included in the repertoire of professional theaters. The artistic self-activity develops its creativity in all types of art and thereby improves and forms. The development of artistic folk art was encouraged by various means. The folk theaters were established in our country in 1953. In 1962, 17 such folk theaters were operating [8]. In 1963, the Azerbaijan Theater Society decided to regularly send directors, artists and actors to assist folk theaters, share creative advices and experience [15]. As a result of about 20 visits to folk theaters in 1963, it became clear that among the folk theaters there were the talented collectives, individual promising amateurs and talented persons. That is why the permanent commission was created in the Theater Society to assist the folk theaters [16]. Thus, in 1969, there were 1.427 artistic self-activity collectives in the country. Among them, 559 choirs, 928 drama groups, 290 choreographic groups, 277 folk instrumental orchestras, 148 instrumental ensembles, 345 artistic propaganda brigades, 425 children's self-activity collectives, etc. can be mentioned [22, p.51]. Already in 1980, 12.549 artistic self-activity collectives with 214.746 participants were operating in the republic [22, p.52]. At the same time, the establishment of "Amateur associations", "Interest clubs", "Youth clubs", "Aesthetic education clubs", etc. clubs were also in the spotlight [22, p.53].

The activity of amateur film studios and film clubs was satisfactory. In 1960, the amateur films were discussed and advices were given at the meetings of the Organizing Bureau of the Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan and the section of the Cinema House for film enthusiasts [12]. Thus, the amateur film studios have been established in the various organizations and institutions [13].

The Azerbaijan Composers Union paid the special attention to the development of young musical collectives – song and dance ensembles. In order to raise their level of creativity, prominent composers, ballet masters and other professional creative intellectuals were assigned to these ensembles. The outstanding composer A.Malikov, while still a student of the Azerbaijan State Conservatory, took an active part in the public service assigned to the artistic self-activity collectives [3]. In 1961 – 1963, the various professional composers gave the creative advices and instructions to youth theaters, artistic self-activity associations, pop orchestras, and choral groups operating in the republic's enterprises and organizations [4].

This creative assistance and cooperation led to the maturation, development, and experience of artistic self-activity collectives, and their formation as increasingly professional creative intellectuals in a purely creative environment.

The Azerbaijan artists used the various forms and methods to promote the development of artistic self-activity associations and collectives. In 1960 – 1961, 10 members of the Union of Artists led the self-activity associations and held advices hours for amateurs [10]. In 1960 – 1961, the republican exhibition of works by amateur artists was held. The target was to reveal young talents through the self-activity. For this purpose, the

Union of Artists organized the seminars and advices hours for amateur artists, held discussions and reviews of their works, organized exhibitions, and took the various practical measures to direct their creative activity [22, p.55].

The Republican Creative Unions, taking the practical action to create a purely creative environment in the country, regularly worked to form the professional, highly intellectual creative persons from young and amateur talented individuals, and constantly fought in the creative and progressive way to achieve the level of professional intellectuals.

2. The role of creative intellectuals in the field of development of Azerbaijan culture

The creative intellectuals – writers, composers, directors, actors, film workers, etc., playing the important role in the development of culture in the country, have always been distinguished by their creative, progressive and positive approach to the various areas of culture, search for new creative ideas and innovations, discovery and professional development of innovation, non – destruction of previous elements and samples, but rather their preservation and development, preservation of the uniqueness of each nation and other characteristic features. From this point of view, the importance of artistic culture, its objective position in the correct formation and enrichment of the people's moral worldview, close acquaintance with the most progressive and positive cultural examples of the world, correct and honest understanding and assimilation of them, right stance against the events, injustice and lawlessness encountered in life, etc. is extremely necessary in resolving issues.

The artistic culture makes the people think, explains, teaches, gives direction, shows what is right and what is wrong, reveals and exposes injustice, invites the people to refrain from bad deeds, educates them, and constantly fight conscientiously and responsibly to bring the most honest and humane features to real life by describing the image of the perfect person. The culture should be understood and understandable by the broad masses of the people and society, express the feelings and desires of the people, combine them in their creative works, write, draw, express, show and disseminate them. Such culture has a deep ideological content, mature artistic craftsmanship, and diverse form, genre and style. The artistic creativity is a complex and multifaceted process, but it is also characterized by its diversity. The artistic creativity is the artistic embodiment and collection of the artistic imagination, the style of ideas, the forms and methods, the various images, thoughts, and ideas created and used in the works by the creative intellectuals such as writers, poets, painters, sculptors, directors, actors, etc. It is extremely important to raise the ideological and political level and professional skills of the creative intellectuals who play the role in the development of culture. Such talented creative intellectuals, represented in the creative unions, fall into a purely creative environment and had the favorable conditions to improve their professional skills, become true professionals, and participate in the development of culture. However, the freedom, independence, and personal liberty given to each artist

in the creative unions to develop their individual characteristics has been the very progressive and positive development and has played the decisive role in the development of culture [21, p.31 – 32]. The Writers` Union (1934), Composers` Union (1934), Artists` Union (1940), and Cinematography Workers Union (1958) were established in Azerbaijan. The Theater Society (1948), the public creative organization of theater

workers in the republic, later transformed into the Theater Workers` Union (1987) [21, p.32]. The role played by these creative unions in the field of development of culture, their participation in cultural construction, the principal position, the functions, the literary and artistic direction they have taken and defined, the development course they have taken, and the activity they have carried out in this regard have been strengthened and consolidated (Image 2).

Image 2. Azerbaijan Creative Unions

Although the ways of creativity, means of expression, fields of activity, the themes they brought to art, the problems they raised, and the levels of craftsmanship of the creative intellectuals who increase their ideological and political levels, and enhance their professional craftsmanship in the creative unions are quite different, the role they play in art – the development of Azerbaijan culture – is undeniable. These creative intellectuals, who differ from each other in their means of expression, beautify art by bringing their interesting thoughts and ideas through “words”, “colors”, “images” and “performances”, who are characterized by their works, images and heroes they created with different but unique and realistic lines, and who are embodied with individual but at the same time progressive and positive elements, are extremely colorful, unique, courageous, realistic, entertaining, thought provoking and educational with the paintings they painted, the fundamental musical works they composed, the beautiful and marvelously animated sculptures they erected, the realistic and artistic – style theater performances they staged, the interesting documentaries and feature films they made, and the diverse roles and performances they played.

Along with the educational, cultural and scientific centers, the creative unions also tried to make their creative contributions to the development of Azerbaijan culture. The creative intellectuals are such a social and professional force that they have the power to directly or indirectly influence the spiritual and moral world, the ideological and political education, the formation of a modern and realistic worldview of the people, the cre-

ation of a perfect and healthy image of a person in society, the strengthening of civic position, the cultivation of a conscious attitude to every issue, and the open expression of people’s ideas and opinions through their creativity. The characteristic features of this period were to instill in people a sense of beauty, the formation of high aesthetic taste, the cultivation of the ability to correctly assess the importance and value of historical and architectural monuments and works of art, the understanding of the phenomenon of personality and other characteristics in order to form them as morally rich, harmoniously developed individuals [22, p.67].

The creative intellectuals develop literature and art, which are the main factors of moral education, create works of art, enrich them with new and progressive ideas, and introduce our republic to other countries. The working mechanism of the Creative Unions, their organizational activity, the attitude towards talented and creative personnel, bringing the problems posed by society and making it think into fiction and culture, the search for unique solutions to important creative questions facing art and artists by the creative intellectuals in their creativity and works, the search for new creativity, the taking of themes of literary works and art examples from real events encountered in life, etc. undoubtedly played the decisive role in the development of culture [21, p.33 – 34].

The literature and art are one of the most fighter spheres of ideological activity [21, p.36]. In order for creative intellectuals to create beautiful works of art, it was necessary for them to be artistically literate, to raise their ideological and political level and to develop their

professional skills. In this regard, the theoretical seminars played the important role. In 1961 – 1962, the Union of Artists organized the lectures and seminars at the Republican Political Education House to raise the ideological and political level of artists of the republic, 67 lectures were read on various topics. Such theoretical seminars were held in almost all creative unions. Sometimes associations were also used for this purpose. Such associations mainly represented those working in literary magazines and the newspaper “Literature and Art” [21, p.38].

One of the areas of activity of the Creative Unions was the improvement of the professional skills of creative intellectuals. For this purpose, advanced training, internships, creative seminars, vacations and business trips, competitions, etc. were organized [21, p.45]. The creative vacations of young creative intellectuals meant the creation of new works of art, new creative searches, finding new themes, bringing them to works of art, the creation, demonstration, promotion of rare examples of art that meet modern requirements, etc. The result of the creative vacation of young artists meant the organization of a report exhibition of their works. The young and professional creative intellectuals of the republic were sent on creative vacations to various countries, including regions. The organization of periodic creative vacations of artists, writers, musicians, directors, film workers and other creative individuals played the exceptional role in the development of culture in our country [21, p.52, 55].

One of the main directions of the activity of the Creative Unions is the organization of work with young people, the identification of talented young persons, the organization of seminars and conferences, the establishment of sections, youth studios, youth clubs, associations of young artists and art critics, youth work commissions, holding youth days, various events, organizing exhibitions of young artists, listening to musical works of young composers, etc., meant the raising of the cultural level of young people, and caring for and assisting in the development of culture [21, p.57]. Thus, in 1963, the first republican gathering of cinema mechanics was held in Baku [18]. In 1964, the meeting of film production and distribution workers was held and dedicated to improving film services to the population [20]. As a result of improving the quality of service in the field of cinematography and cinema, taking specific practical measures in this sphere, by 1965 there were 1.340 cinemas and film facilities under the Republican Cinematography Committee [14]. The documentaries, animated films, etc. were shown in genre film clubs operating in some cinemas of Baku. Among them, it is possible to mention the “Cinema distribution` courier”, “Kaleidoscope”, “Club of movie lovers” and “Heritage” repeated film hall. In 1986, the repertoire of these film clubs included more than 200 works – feature films, documentaries, animated films, etc. [22, p.90]. However, it should be noted that although the importance of scientific – popular, historical – chronicle, chronicle – documentary, and educational films was very great, they were not given enough space in the development of cinematography and the creative process.

At the same time, there was a need to apply the achievements of modern science and technology during the production of motion pictures.

The demonstration of the activity of creative intellectuals and their works can be considered a kind of creative report on the work done in the field of development of culture. In this regard, the exhibitions of works by artists, composers, playwrights, theater and cinema figures were organized, photo stands and photo albums reflecting their activity were prepared, their works were included in radio and television programs, performances were prepared, films were shown, the importance of the roles they play was studied and analyzed by art historians and literary critics. The various new works, theater performances, documentaries and feature films were presented to the audience for discussion, their objective, progressive ideas and opinions were taken into account [22, p.90].

In 1960, four brigades consisting of actors from the Opera and Ballet Theater, the Young Spectator Theater, and members of the Theater Society were organized to deliver reports on thematic topics at the various institutions and organizations of the republic [22, p.91].

The Azerbaijan Creative Unions were engaged in theoretical and practical activities in the field of development of culture, forming their creative and organizational work. One of the most important tasks facing the creative intellectuals represented in the creative unions, associations and societies was to constantly work and struggle for the creation of works of high artistic quality. For to raise the ideological and artistic level of works of art, the disputes, discussions, round tables, competitions and reviews of works were organized. The creative and organizational work carried out by the unions was one of the main field of their activity. The deep scientific research of the active theoretical and practical activities of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the republic was conducted by Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva. The talented historian, the great expert in this field, the researcher of the current issues of Azerbaijan culture, the activity of creative intellectuals in the field of development of culture, and the role, place and activity of Creative Unions in the field of culture in the 1960 – 1980s of XXth century, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva played the exceptional role in the study of creative intelligentsia and creativity issues with her fundamental scientific works. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva’s textbook “ The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda (1960 – 1980s)” (1990) [22], the book “The cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions (1960 – 1980s)” (1991) [23] and the monograph “The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of development of culture (1960 – 1980s)” (2014) [21] are the fundamental scientific and research works dedicated to the activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions and the role played by creative intellectuals in the field of development of culture in the republic. The researcher notes that the struggle for the writing of works of high artistic quality occupied a central place in the activity of creative unions [21, p.76]. The Writers` Union discussed the issue of creating a human image in works of art, the reflection of the friendship of peoples in Azerbaijan literature, the introduction of humanist ideas into

fiction and other actual issues at its mobile plenums in 1970 and 1971 [21, p.78,79]. The role of literary and artistic criticism in raising the ideological and artistic level of literary and artistic works was also emphasized here [21, p.79]. This was engaged by the criticism departments of the Writers` Union bodies. The Writers` Union paid the special attention to solving the creative problems, preparing and listening to creative reports [21, p.80, 81].

The creative intellectuals during this period constantly worked and fought for the literary and artistic works they created to be a perfect example of creativity, artistically and morally perfect, with a solid composition, based on a correct plot line, complete human images, and colorful means of expression [21, p.87]. They tried to ensure that theatrical performances and films not only educated the audience with their content, but also reflected the novelty of form, the richness of human character, and the characteristic features of life. At the same time, the creative intellectuals tried to avoid stereotypes, primitiveness, standard themes, to apply courageous searches, innovation, new genres and the importance of solving creative problems in their works of art [21, p.105]. The role of creative intellectuals in the development of Azerbaijan culture was very specific and diverse, and in the 60 – 80s of the XXth century it passed the very successful and at the same time glorious way, rich in creative struggle. The role played by the creative intellectuals in the development of all spheres of culture greatly enriched, developed Azerbaijan culture and led to the creation of unique examples of art, rich in progressive – realistic features, based only on accurate facts and to some extent on the creative imagination of the artist.

Conclusion

The culture is an integral part of every nation. The nation that does not develop its culture cannot understand itself and cannot take its rightful place among other nations. The creative intellectuals are innovative, progressive worldview, mature and creative individuals who constantly work in the various spheres of this culture, develop and enrich it, create and promote new and perfect examples of art, literature and works of art, are in search of new creativity, and bring new thoughts and ideas to art. Guided by the ideas of realism, they enrich these themes with a bit of artistic imagination and, by combining them, create incomparable works, paintings, drawings, sculptures, beautiful performances, interesting films, fundamental musical works, etc. literary and artistic masterpieces. Each work is a set of specific themes, a single plot line, a unity of images, an event that the writer or artist intended and wanted to describe. This unity connects images, embodies elements together, and connects each episode with the general essence of an event or problem. The creative intellectuals express this unity with their talent and skills, creating unique examples of art. The culture owes for its development to the great labor, boundless talent, skill and ability, and creative craftsmanship of these creative intellectuals.

In the 60 – 80s of the XXth century, the creative intelligentsia of Azerbaijan did the great work with their scientific and artistic activities, participating in the solution and research of actual problems of culture. The

role of the creative intelligentsia in the development of Azerbaijan culture was quite diverse and singled out for its special activity and relevance in the 60 – 80s of the XXth century. The extensive activity of creative intellectuals during this period has been carefully, conscientiously and great responsibly examined in the scientific works and fundamental scientific research works of our valuable researchers and has found their scientific solution.

Azerbaijan culture is proud of its creative intellectuals. They have done a great deal in very short period of time and have managed to develop each sphere of culture separately. The culture is like iron, as it is worked, read, written, performed, and understood, it develops, becomes perfect, embodies the progressive thoughts and ideas, and always pleases refined tastes. In this regard, the role of creative intellectuals in the field of development of Azerbaijan culture in the 60 – 80s of the XXth century is undeniable and occupies one of the most worthy places. The talented researchers of our country, conscientiously and responsibly investigating this honorable role and activity of creative intellectuals, demonstrated the intellectual position and highly appreciated the great and honorable work of intellectuals – creative intelligentsia, and dedicated the fundamental works to this valuable activity.

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